

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 71

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 71

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 71:1 "In You, O LORD, I have taken refuge; Let me never be ashamed. ² "In Your righteousness deliver me and rescue me; ^bIncline Your ear to me and save me. ³ "Be to me a rock of ^bhabitation to which I may continually come; You have given ^ccommandment to save me, For You are ^dmy ¹rock and my fortress. ⁴ "Rescue me, O my God, out of the hand of the wicked, Out of the ¹grasp of the wrongdoer and ruthless man, ⁵ For You are my ^ahope; O Lord ¹GOD, <i>You are</i> my ^bconfidence from my youth. ⁶ ¹By You I have been ^asustained from <i>my</i> birth; You are He who ^btook me from my mother's womb; My ^cpraise is continually ²of You.</p>	<p>Psa. 71:1 בְּךָ-יְהוָה חָסִיתִי אֶל-אֲבוֹשָׁה לְעוֹלָם : ² בְּצַדִּיקְתְּךָ תִצִּילֵנִי וְתַכֵּלֵטֵנִי הִטָּה-אֵלַי אָזְנוֹךָ וְהוֹשִׁיעֵנִי : ³ הִיְהִי לִי אֶלְצוּר מְעוֹן לָבוֹא תִמְיֵד צְרִיחַתִּי לְהוֹשִׁיעֵנִי כִי- סִלַּעַי וּמְצוּדֹתַי אֶתָּה : ⁴ אֱלֹהֵי פִלְטֵנִי מִיַּד רָשָׁע מִכַּף מְעַוְלֵל וְחוֹמֵץ : ⁵ כִּי- אַתָּה תִקְוֹתִי אֲדֹנָי יְהוִה מִבִּטְחֵי מִנְעוּרַי : ⁶ עַל־יָךְ נִסְמַכְתִּי מִבֶּטֶן מִמְעַי אִמִּי אַתָּה גֹזַנִי בְךָ תִהְלַתִּי תִמְיֵד : ⁷ כַּמּוֹפֵת תִּהְיֶיתִי לְרַבִּים וְאַתָּה מִחֲסִי-עוֹ : ⁸ יִמְלֵא בִי תִהְלֶתְךָ כָּל-הַיּוֹם תִּפְאֶרֶתְךָ : ⁹ אֶל-תִּשְׁלִיכֵנִי לַעֲתָה זְקַנְהָ כְּכֹלֹת כֹּחֵי אֶל- תַּעֲזֹבֵנִי : ¹⁰ כִּי-אָמְרוּ אוֹיְבָי לִי וְשֹׁמְרֵי נַפְשִׁי נוֹעְצוּ</p>
<p>Psa. 71:7 I have become a ^amarvel to many, For You are ^bmy strong refuge. ⁸ My ^amouth is filled with Your praise And with ^bYour glory all day long. ⁹ Do not cast me off in the ^atime of old age; Do not forsake me when my strength fails.</p>	

¹⁰ For my enemies have spoken
¹against me;
 And those who “watch for my ²life
^bhave consulted together,
¹¹ Saying, ““God has forsaken him;
 Pursue and seize him, for there is
^bno one to deliver.”

Psa. 71:12 O God, “do not be far from
 me;

O my God, ^bhasten to my help!
¹³ Let those who are adversaries of
 my soul be “ashamed *and* consumed;
 Let them be ^bcovered with
 reproach and dishonor, who ‘seek ¹to
 injure me.

¹⁴ But as for me, I will “hope
 continually,
 And will ^{1b}praise You yet more
 and more.

¹⁵ My “mouth shall tell of Your
 righteousness
And of ^bYour salvation all day
 long;

For I ‘do not know the ¹sum of
them.

¹⁶ I will come “with the mighty deeds
 of the Lord ¹GOD;
 I will ^bmake mention of Your
 righteousness, Yours alone.

Psa. 71:17 O God, You “have taught
 me from my youth,
 And I still ^bdeclare Your
 wondrous deeds.

¹⁸ And even when *I am* “old and
 gray, O God, do not forsake me,
 Until I ^bdeclare Your ¹strength to
this generation,

Your power to all who are to
 come.

יִתְּרוֹ : ¹¹ לֵאמֹר אֱלֹהִים עֲזָבוּ
 רִדְפוֹ וְתַפְשׁוּהוּ כִּי־אֵין
 מִצִּיל : ¹² אֱלֹהִים אֶל־תִּרְחַק
 מִמְּנֵי אֱלֹהֵי לְעִזְרָתִי חִישָׁה
 [חִישָׁה :] ¹³ יִבְשׁוּ יְכֹלֹ שִׁטְנֵי
 נַפְשֵׁי יַעֲטוּ חֲרָפָה וּכְלָמָה
 מִבְּקִשֵׁי רָעָתִי : ¹⁴ וְאֲנִי תָמִיד
 אֶיִתֵּל וְהוֹסַפְתִּי עַל־כָּל־
 תַּהֲלָתְךָ : ¹⁵ פִּי אֵי־סֹפֵר
 צְדָקָתְךָ כָּל־הַיּוֹם תִּשׁוּעָתְךָ
 כִּי לֹא יִדַּעְתִּי סִפְרוֹת : ¹⁶
 אֲבוֹא בַּגְּבוּרֹת אֲדַנֶּי יְהוָה
 אֲזַכִּיר צְדָקָתְךָ לְבִדְךָ : ¹⁷
 אֱלֹהִים לְמִדְתַּנִּי מִנְּעוּרַי
 וְעַד־הַנְּהָ אֲגִיד נִפְלְאוֹתֶיךָ :
¹⁸ וְגַם עַד־זְקֻנָּה אֲשִׁיבָה
 אֱלֹהִים אֶל־תַּעֲזֹבֵנִי עַד־
 אֲגִיד זִרְעֶךָ לְדוֹר לְכָל־
 יָבוֹא גְבוּרָתְךָ : ¹⁹ וְצְדָקָתְךָ
 אֱלֹהִים עַד־מָרוֹם אֲשֶׁר־
 עָשִׂיתָ גְדֻלוֹת אֱלֹהִים מִי
 כָּמוֹךָ : ²⁰ אֲשֶׁר הִרְאִיתָנוּ
 [הִרְאִיתָנוּ] צָרוֹת רַבּוֹת

¹⁹ ¹For Your ^arighteousness, O God,
reaches to the ²heavens,

You who have ^bdone great things;
O God, ‘who is like You?

²⁰ You who have ^ashown ¹me many
troubles and distresses

Will ^brevive ¹me again,

And will bring ¹me up again ‘from
the depths of the earth.

²¹ May You increase my ^agreatness
And turn *to* ^bcomfort me.

Psa. 71:22 I will also praise You with
^{1a}a harp,
Even Your ²truth, O my God;
To You I will sing praises with the
^blyre,

O ‘Holy One of Israel.

²³ My lips will ^ashout for joy when I
sing praises to You;

And my ^bsoul, which You have
redeemed.

²⁴ My ^atongue also will utter Your
righteousness all day long;

For they are ^bashamed, for they are
humiliated who seek ¹my hurt.

וְרָעוֹת תָּשׁוּב תִּחְיֶינּוּ
[תִּחְיֶינּוּ] וּמִהַמּוֹת הָאָרֶץ
תָּשׁוּב תֵּעָלֵנִי : ²¹ תִּתְרַב |
גִּדְלֹתַי וְתִסָּב תִּנְחַמְנִי : ²²
גַּם-אֲנִי אֲוֹדֶךָ בְּכָל-נְבִלֹ
אֲמַתְךָ אֵלֶיךָ אֲזַמְרָה לְךָ
בְּכִנּוֹר קָדוֹשׁ יִשְׂרָאֵל : ²³
תִּרְנְנָה שִׁפְתַי כִּי אֲזַמְרָה-
לְךָ וְנִפְשִׁי אֲשֶׁר פָּדִיתָ : ²⁴
גַּם-לְשׁוֹנִי כָל-הַיּוֹם תִּהְיֶינָה
צְדָקָתְךָ כִּי-בָשׁוּ כִי-חָפְרוּ
מִבְּקָשֵׁי רַעְתִּי :

References

Psalm 71:1

^aPs 25:2, 3; 31:1-3; 71:1-3

Psalm 71:2

^aPs 31:1

^bPs 17:6

Psalm 71:3

¹Or *crag*

^aPs 31:2, 3

^bDeut 33:27; Ps 90:1; 91:9

^cPs 7:6; 42:8

^dPs 18:2

Psalm 71:4

¹Lit *palm*

^aPs 140:1, 4

Psalm 71:5

¹Heb *YHWH*, usually rendered *LORD*

^aPs 39:7; Jer 14:8; 17:7, 13, 17; 50:7

^bPs 22:9

Psalm 71:6

¹Lit *Upon You I have been supported*

²Lit *in*

^aPs 22:10; Is 46:3

^bJob 10:18; Ps 22:9

^cPs 34:1

Psalm 71:7

^aIs 8:18; 1 Cor 4:9

^bPs 61:3

Psalm 71:8

^aPs 35:28; 63:5

^bPs 96:6; 104:1

Psalm 71:9

^aPs 71:18; 92:14; Is 46:4

Psalm 71:10

¹Lit *with reference to*

²Lit *soul*

^aPs 56:6

^bPs 31:13; 83:3; Matt 27:1

Psalm 71:11

^aPs 3:2

^bPs 7:2

Psalm 71:12

^aPs 10:1; 22:11; 35:22; 38:21

^bPs 38:22; 40:13; 70:1, 5

Psalm 71:13

¹Lit *my injury*

^aPs 35:4, 26; 40:14

^bPs 109:29

^cEsth 9:2; Ps 71:24

Psalm 71:14

¹Lit *add upon all Your praise*

^aPs 130:7

^bPs 71:8

Psalm 71:15

¹Lit *numbers*

^aPs 35:28

^bPs 96:2

^cPs 40:5

Psalm 71:16

¹Heb *YHWH*, usually rendered *LORD*

^aPs 106:2

^bPs 51:14

Psalm 71:17

^aDeut 4:5; 6:7

^bPs 26:7; 40:5; 119:27

Psalm 71:18

¹Lit *arm*

^aPs 71:9

^bPs 22:31; 78:4, 6

Psalm 71:19

¹Or *And*

²Lit *height*

^aPs 36:6; 57:10

^bPs 126:2; Luke 1:49

^cDeut 3:24; Ps 35:10

Psalm 71:20

¹Another reading is *us*

^aPs 60:3

^bPs 80:18; 85:6; 119:25; 138:7; Hos 6:1, 2

^cPs 86:13

Psalm 71:21

^aPs 18:35

^bPs 23:4; 86:17; Is 12:1; 49:13

Psalm 71:22

¹Lit *an instrument of a harp*

²Or *faithfulness*

^aPs 33:2; 81:2; 92:1-3; 144:9

^bPs 33:2; 147:7

^c2 Kin 19:22; Ps 78:41; 89:18; Is 1:4

Psalm 71:23

^aPs 5:11; 32:11; 132:9, 16

^bPs 34:22; 55:18; 103:4

Psalm 71:24

¹Or *to injure me*

^aPs 35:28

^bPs 71:13

Targum

Psa. 71:1 In your word, O LORD, I have put my trust; I will never be disappointed.²
In your generosity deliver me and save me; incline your ear to me and redeem me.³
Be a strong mighty rock for me always to come to; you have given commandment to
redeem me, for you are my strength and my stout fortress.⁴ O God, save me from the
hand of the wicked man, from the hand of the wrongdoer and the predator.⁵ For you
are my hope, O LORD; my God, my confidence from my youth.⁶ I have relied on
you from the womb; you bring me out of the bowels of my mother; my Psalm is
always of your word.⁷ I have become like a portent for many; and you are my
confidence and my strength.⁸ My mouth will be filled with your praise, with your
splendor every day.⁹ Do not cast me away at the time of old age; when my vigor
ceases, do not forsake me.¹⁰ For my enemies have spoken evil about me, and those
who watch my soul have conspired together.¹¹ Saying, “God has forsaken him; pursue
and catch him, for there is no one to deliver [him].”¹² O God, do not be far from me;
O my God, hasten to my aid.¹³ Let those who oppose my soul be disappointed [and]
destroyed; let those who seek my ruin be covered with disgrace and dishonor.¹⁴ And I
will always wait, and I will add to all your praise.¹⁵ My mouth will tell of your
generosity, of your redemption every day, for I do not know their number.¹⁶ I will
enter in the strength of the LORD God; I will remember your righteousness alone.¹⁷
O my God, you have taught me by miracles from my youth; and to this very time I
will tell of your marvels.¹⁸ And moreover, O God, do not forsake me at the time of
old age and gray hair, until I may tell of the strength of your arm to every generation,
of your mighty strength to all who will come.¹⁹ Your righteousness, O God, [reaches]
to the highest heaven, for you have done great things; O God, who is like you?²⁰ You
who have shown me great and evil troubles, make us live again; and bring us up again
from the deepest depths.²¹ You will increase my greatness, and you will turn and
comfort me.²² Also I will give thanks in your presence with instruments of song, and
the lyre; I will tell of your truth, O my God, I will sing praise in your presence with
the harp, Holy One of Israel.²³ My lips will rejoice, for I will give praise in your
presence, and [also] my soul that you have redeemed.²⁴ Also my tongue every day will
repeat your generosity, for those who seek my ruin have been disappointed, they have
been put to shame. --

Spiritual Awareness

Due to the length of the Psalm, only the spiritual awareness of verses will be explored.

Introduction

This Psalm is a continuation of Psalm 70. David was near his death and feared he might not live to regain his royal throne. He, therefore, pleaded with God to rejuvenate him. Absalom, David's son, had started a rebellion against his father. At one point during the rebellion, Absalom conquered Jerusalem. He was ready to declare himself King. David fled from Jerusalem before Absalom could capture him. Eventually, David did stop the rebellion. At the writing of this Psalm, David was concerned that he would not be able to regain the throne. He wanted to live up to what the LORD wanted him to do. The rebellion occurred because of David's immoral affair with Bathsheba.

Verse two

David knew that, eventually, the LORD would deliver him from the rebellion. He pleaded with the LORD to allow him to escape the rebellion's destruction. David prayed to deliver him back to the throne.

**In Your merciful justice You will deliver me and You will let me escape;
now incline Your ear to me and save me.**

Verse five

There is a balance between justice and mercy in the LORD's Universe. The Sefirot Gevurah and Chesed are the top of two of the three columns in the Tree of Life. How can mercy be shown when justice is needed?

For You have been my hope; my Master, Who shows mercy from the Sefirah Chesed even as the Seforah Gevurah is giving out justice. You have had my trust from my youth.

Verse six

David did not have a happy childhood. He was the youngest of eight sons and not well-treated by his older brothers. His father misunderstood him and made him a shepherd over the flocks. When Samuel came to Jesse's house to find the next King of Israel, David was almost overlooked. David found little love and understanding from his nuclear family, forcing him to look to his inner resources for comfort.

On You I relied for support from birth; You have set me apart from my mother's womb; from You it would always come about whatever was to be praise worthy in me.

Verses twelve and thirteen

The gravity of David's sin was quite enormous. However, David asked the LORD to remain close to him even now as the Sefirah Gevurah passes judgment.

O God, be not far from me; O my God, make haste to help me.

Verse Fifteen

David did not understand how the Tree of Life worked. Therefore, he did not know how Chesed and Gevurah went hand in hand.

My mouth shall tell of Your merciful justice, and of your Salvation every day, for I have never know how to emmeraete them.

Verse nineteen

The power of the ten Sefirot radiate from Heaven into all areas of the Universe.

For Your merciful justice reaches into high heavens, O You who have done great things, O God, who is like you?

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

